

Evaluation of 26 insecticides for armyworm *Mythimna separata* Walker) control

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Rice is sporadically damaged by *M. separata* larvae, which attack rice at all growth stages but are most damaging during heading, when they cut rice panicles. Insecticides with a high knockdown effect control this insect best.

We evaluated 26 insecticides for *M. separata* control in a contact toxicity test. Larvae were dipped into each insecticide solution for 30 s and then placed on untreated plants. In a foliar spray test, potted rice plants were sprayed with insecticide and infested with untreated larvae 1 d later. Mortality was recorded 48 h after treatment (HT) or infestation (HI), and leaf damage was rated.

Of the 26 insecticides, 17 caused 100% mortality in contact toxicity tests, 13 caused more than 80% mortality in foliar spray tests, and 12 caused 10% defoliation. High mortality did not necessarily correlate with low defoliation (see table).

Twelve insecticides were highly promising and four (U 57770, RH 0994, MTI 500, and MTI 220) were potentially promising. Cypermethrin killed insects and prohibited larvae from feeding (see table). *J*

Toxicity of insecticides to *M. separata*, IIRRI.

Insecticide ^a	Formulation	Mortality ^b (%) of 5th-instar larvae		
		Contact toxicity	Foliar spray	Defoliation (%)
<i>Test I</i>				
Methidathion	40EC	100 a	90 ab	10
M 9918	200E	100 a	100 a	10
Cypermethrin †	5EC	97 a	33 a	10
UC SF-1	40F	100 a	70 bcd	10
M 10604	200E	100 a	97 ab	10
UC 54229	100SP	100 a	41 cde	63
RH 0308	48EC	100 a	93 ab	10
UC/MP 19779	48EC	100 a	77 abc	10
Carbosulfan	20EC	97 a	90 ab	10
UC 17867	50WP	100 a	93 ab	10
Monocrotophos	30EC	100 a	100 a	10
Triazophos	40EC	100 a	93 ab	10
Dioxcarb	50WP	73 b	20 ef	63
Methiocarb	50WP	97 a	30 def	63
RH 0994	48EC	100 a	87 ab	11
Dioxathion	96EC	17 c	7 f ^g	83
Check (water)		0 c	10 f ^g	90
<i>Test II</i>				
Phoxim	50EC	100 a	67 b	27
NS 8265	75EC	100 a	0 c	93
Propoxur	20EC	97 a	3 c	90
MTI 500 †	20EC	100 a	90 ab	17
Pirimicarb + pirimiphos methyl	10EC	100 a	10 c	97
Pirimiphos methyl + carbophenothion	20EC	100 a	0 c	93
U 57710	85WP	63 b	87 ab	13
Monocrotophos	30EC	100 a	98 a	10
Triazophos	40EC	100 a	100 a	10
U 56295	85WP	70 b	93 a	10
MTI 220 †	20EC	100 a	83 ab	20
B. thuringiensis ‡		0 e	0 c	91
Check (water)		0 e	0 c	93

^a Application rate was 0.075% ai in the contact toxicity test, except for the pyrethroids (...), which was 0.005% ai; and 0.75 kg ai in the foliar spray test except for †, which was 0.05 kg ai/ha. For ‡, the rate was 0.4 kg/ha of the formulated product. ^bAv of 3 replications. Mortality was recorded 48 h after treatment in the contact toxicity tests and 48 h after placing the larvae on treated plants in the foliar spray test. Separation of means in a column under each test by DMRT at the 5% level.

A strategic modelling approach to brown planthopper (BPH) management

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We monitored populations of BPH and associated rice fauna at a field site in

Laguna, Philippines, throughout each growing season from 1979 to 1983. These data and other information obtained from the literature are being used to construct a population model to explain BPH population dynamics observed on rice crops at different Philippine sites. The model will subsequently be used to study the impact of BPH on changes in management, including resistant varieties and insecticides, in different climatic zones.

Two modelling techniques are being used. Initially, interaction matrices and other qualitative modelling techniques were used to identify the major relationships between components likely to contribute to BPH population changes.

The interaction matrix is shown in Figure 1. Each cell is concerned with the primary effect of the column component on the row component. Secondary effects can be determined by working

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